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Innovative methods of teaching Sustainable Development

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ABSTRACT

Solutions to problems related to Sustainable Development require a complex, multidisciplinary approach. Experts representing the fields of engineering and natural sciences, as well as social sciences should collaborate in order to achieve meaningful, long term results in the environmental, social and economic domains of sustainability. This requires a shift in how we understand problems and how we develop solutions to them.

However, current teaching practices are not able to develop the knowledge and skills required for the solution of our contemporary problems. For this reason, new, innovative methods of teaching are required, especially in higher education.

In this article we identify the most important limitations of traditional teaching methods and will also make an effort to provide an overview of available innovative methods currently used around the world. We will share our experiences with three specific innovative teaching methods we used over the last ten years: 1) role plays, which simulate negotiation processes dealing with global environmental and social problems; 2) teaching through consultation projects with the participation of civil sector organisations (NGOs) and 3) social innovation labs, which have been growing all around the world and which promote a better understanding of the environmental and social implications of new technological solutions.

Our experiences show that these methods do not only teach invaluable knowledge and skills (e.g. creativity, team decision making, negotiation skills, etc.) to the participating students, but also provide them with a once in a lifetime experience of facing real world problems and inventing solutions to them.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Transforming our society to a more sustainable one requires decision makers who have a deeper understanding of our current challenges, can take a holistic view while working out solutions to them and possess a set of hard and soft skills to evoke real change. Educating students to become such decision makers – so that they can elaborate innovative, appropriate and widely acceptable solutions to the complex and highly intertwined problems of our world – requires innovative, new methods of teaching in institutions of higher education.

This paper provides an overview of the nature of sustainability challenges and how this should be reflected in higher education. Based on the literature and our practical experiences, we provide evidence why traditional teaching methods cannot be successful to adequately address the complexity of sustainability issues. Then we introduce three innovative teaching methods, namely, role plays, Pro Bono consultancy projects and social innovation labs, which were designed to equip students with knowledge and skills crucial to create truly sustainable solutions.

We argue that there is an urgent need to integrate new, innovative methods in the education of all disciplines, not only those focusing on sustainable development. Our experiences show that using such innovative methods of teaching do not only make studying more engaging and enjoyable to students, but also significantly contribute to a lasting learning experience.

2. REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

2.1 The nature of sustainability challenges

Sustainable development is often defined in relation to human welfare, which in turn is dependent on our natural and social environment (see e.g. [1]). Major crisis situations relating to these brought about an explosion of discourse about the meaning and nature of sustainable development, as well as potential ways of achieving it.

While we still lack consensus regarding many facets of sustainability, most experts agree that sustainable development should integrate at least three broad areas: the natural, social and economic domains related to human existence.

Most challenges to implement sustainable development can be considered as wicked problems. Originally using the term in social policy planning, Rittel and Webber defined wicked problems using the following criteria [2]:

1. There is no definitive formulation of a wicked problem
2. Wicked problems have no stopping rule
3. Solutions to wicked problems are not true-or-false, but good-or-bad
4. There is no immediate and no ultimate test of a solution to a wicked problem
5. Every solution to a wicked problem is a "one-shot operation"; because there is no opportunity to learn by trial and error, every attempt counts significantly
6. Wicked problems do not have an enumerable (or an exhaustively describable) set of potential solutions, nor is there a well-described set of permissible operations that may be incorporated into the plan
7. Every wicked problem is essentially unique
8. Every wicked problem can be considered to be a symptom of another problem

9. The existence of a discrepancy representing a wicked problem can be explained in numerous ways. The choice of explanation determines the nature of the problem's resolution
10. The planner has no right to be wrong.

Taking human induced climate change as an example, one can easily see its 'wicked' nature. Debate about its existence, extent, nature and urgency is still on the agenda in spite of considerable research effort on behalf of various scientific disciplines. It is even challenging to define what the desired state of global climate should be, let alone how and with what tools to achieve it. The solution to the climate issue cannot utilize (or only to a very limited extent) our previous experiences with other wicked problems. For example, lessons learnt and solutions developed to solve the depletion of the ozone layer cannot be transferred directly – if at all – to climate change efforts. Climate change, being a threat to human welfare itself, has implications for many other sustainability issues including eco-system health, the provision of drinking water and food, as well as various related social issues.

Similar to climate change, many other sustainability challenges can be identified as wicked problems: environmental issues such as species extinction, the degradation of the soil, the pollution of the oceans and social issues such as access to basic amenities, education and the job market, violation of human rights and conflicts over natural resources are only a few of the many examples. In fact, the 17 priority topics identified by the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals cover issues that can be understood as wicked problems.

Taking an engineering methodology point of view, Yearworth identifies sustainability as a 'super-wicked' problem using the additional concerns of Bernstein et al.: „(i) time is running out, (ii) no one authority is in control, (iii) we are the cause of the problem anyway, and (iv) we inherently discount the future in our everyday decision-making” ([3] in: [4]). Taking our previous example further, it is easy to see how problems related to climate change can be considered 'super-wicked'.

While identifying sustainability challenges as wicked problems does not make them any easier to solve, this approach can provide us with some insight regarding how to prepare the future generations so that they can elaborate appropriate solutions to them.

2.2 Implications for higher education

According to Svanström et al. [5] the integration of different perspectives and the concept of sustainability is challenging because it makes systemic and holistic thinking and radically innovative ways of education necessary.

With the deepening of our understanding in every discipline, the scientific method of working in silos is more justified than ever, since it is needed to promote excellence and even newer results. However, the tackling of wicked problems, such as many sustainability challenges, also requires that we build bridges between these silos. The need for such an interdisciplinary approach is widely accepted in both science and education.

To some extent, engineering education has already opened up to the ideas deriving from other disciplines (e.g. some aspects of social sciences). However, efforts to

integrate various scientific domains in higher education often do not reach their objectives. Students and professors are preoccupied with their home territories and either do not understand the necessity of the interdisciplinary approach or are too busy pursuing their own research agendas.

Management education also suffers from taking a narrow perspective: how businesses should react to changing stakeholder demands and how the sustainability challenge will influence their bottom lines. On the contrary, ethical issues, complex problems and social responsibility are softer areas, which would require careful consideration, emotional intelligence and – as a result – different teaching approaches [6].

Innovative methods of teaching sustainability are also necessary, because the intensity of student involvement is a significant factor in the shaping of their opinions and behaviour regarding environmental and social issues (see e.g. [5], [7], [8] and [9]).

Traditional teaching methods often focus purely on the transfer of factual knowledge, which may raise concern and awareness, but has clear limitations regarding achieving behavioural change ([10] and [11]). While being necessary drivers for action, even changes in attitudes and values have been found insufficient to alter behaviour in a predictable way ([12] and [13]). Shaping the school as a social setting, raising interest in sustainability topics and commitment to them is crucial in determining the relationship between sustainability education and sustainable behaviour [9].

According to Kerekes and Wetzker over the coming years more effort should be put into developing teaching methods than into developing content in management education [6]. There are three well-known arguments which support this proposition. First, the e-society requires to rethink the ways of teaching because it creates a new kind of student and permanently changes the quality of information they have access to. Second, the expectations and demands of well-educated students are also changing. The value of soft skills is increasing, while the value of factual knowledge is decreasing. Creativity, convincing communication, collaboration skills, empathy and other forms of social behaviour are attributes that employers are looking for. Third, “Planet Earth has become a global village. Everything is interconnected. Complexity and uncertainty dictate business. These things cannot be described accurately with simple, deterministic tools” (ibid. p.18).

Several papers are emphasizing the role of higher education institutions in representing and supporting the values, knowledge and actions in order to prepare students to be change agents and transform society from unsustainable, irresponsible to more sustainable and responsible patterns ([9], [14] and [15]). The integration of sustainability issues into university curricula and the teaching methods are discussed among others by O’Brien and Sarkis [16], Steiner and Posch [17], as well as Du et al. [18]. An ultimate message from those papers is that motivation and perceived effectiveness are key factors of behavioural change (see also [26]).

3. METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH AND LESSONS LEARNT

The authors of this paper have been actively involved in teaching various topics related to sustainable development over the last 25 years both to engineering and business students. Our experiences cover traditional teaching methods, as well as innovative solutions to engage students in the form of curricular or extra-curricular activities.

In the following sections we introduce three innovative teaching methods, which have gained popularity in recent years in the education of sustainable development: role plays, Pro Bono projects and social/sustainability innovation labs.

We will concentrate on the potential benefits, the requirements and limitations of each of these innovative solutions as we experienced them at the Budapest University of Technology and Economics and the Corvinus University of Budapest during the past years and will make suggestions for their use in university education.

3.1. Role plays and simulation games

The exposition of the complexity of sustainability related problems is one area, where traditional classroom based teaching methods often fail. While students learn about the different domains of sustainable development, namely the economic, social and environmental aspects of development, the interrelatedness of these domains and the need for integrated solutions is hard to comprehend.

Additionally, students of engineering and business programs master their specific disciplines during their studies, but learn little about the political context, which has a major impact on how innovative solutions can gain a foothold and generate change towards a more sustainable society.

One way of familiarizing young people with real life problems and their solutions is teaching through simulations/role plays where the complexity of contemporary economic, social and environmental issues and the need for interdisciplinary solutions can be exposed.

Role plays may serve several objectives and may focus on a wide variety of issues, local, regional or global in nature, but apart from providing a bigger picture than usual classroom activities, they can also improve a number of useful skills, such as negotiation, communication and speaking in public, problem solution, team work and facilitation skills, etc.

One such initiative is the worldwide series of Model UN conferences organised since the late 1940's, but dating back even earlier to the Model League of Nations simulations. A Model UN Conference is an extra-curricular activity for students who play the role of delegates to the United Nations and simulate the negotiation processes within UN committees. Model UN conferences are often initiated by high schools and universities with the active participation of students in the organisation of the event. Students take on the roles of UN representatives, members of other international bodies and national cabinets and learn about the workings of international politics and problem-solving (mun.bme.hu).

In Spring, 2019 a Model UN Conference, namely the BME Model UN Conference was held at BME for the second time with about 100 participating students. While this is a small number compared to other Model UN events, the professional quality of the Conference was high and attracted students from 35 countries.

The main objectives of the Model UN Conference at BME are:

- “to build relationships beyond classrooms, facilitate learning and to develop intercultural dialogue
- to make students understand the world around them, that their contribution as a global citizen is a must for a greater tomorrow

- to provide an interactive educational experience that teaches in an interesting and enjoyable way about the United Nations and
- to make students realize the power of dialogue in solving global issues” (mun.bme.hu)

Experiences of two Model UN conferences at BME show that students are eager to engage in such events, which help them gain a deeper and at the same time more holistic understanding of contemporary social problems. Participants at the BME Model UN Conferences have diverse backgrounds, many representing various engineering disciplines, but students studying business and natural sciences also joined the Conference. The emphasis of this type of diversity has major implications for finding and implementing solutions in real world scenarios later during the participants’ career.

Another innovative teaching tool developed by Paschall and Wüstenhagen addresses the complexities of the international negotiation process relating to human induced climate change [19]. Combating climate change became one of the biggest challenges of this century and the ability of our societies to solve this challenge significantly depends on the complex understanding and appropriate mindset of current and future decision makers. Paschall and Wüstenhagen developed a “multischool negotiation simulation that is unique in its intensiveness, cross-sector design, and transdisciplinary nature” [21]. The course called “Model UNFCCC – Climate Strategy Role Play” has been offered to students jointly for 11 years by the most renowned universities of the CEMS network across Europe ending in a two-day long simulation of a climate summit, with the participation of 100-150 students.

The authors of this paper have themselves been teaching this very special and innovative course for several years. According to the experience of the teaching staff in the participating countries, the level of enthusiasm and the impact of the course on expected learning outcomes, awareness and commitment of students towards finding viable solutions to the climate challenge and sustainability problems in general, are exceptionally high, compared to traditional courses.

The main objectives of the course are:

- To provide students a deeper understanding of the negotiation process under the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), the difficulties of how to reconcile the often opposing interests of negotiating parties, including governments, sector-specific industry associations, global companies and environmental & humanitarian non-governmental organizations (NGOs);
- To highlight the interconnections between corporate strategies and public policies.
- To provide students a highly interactive and fully international simulation situation, where they need to be able to effectively negotiate, according to the mutual gains approach of negotiation, in order to develop consensus solutions, while gaining a better understanding of bilateral and multilateral negotiation dynamics, related to climate change.

The course consists of four modules, covering an extensive introduction to the topic of climate change and climate policy, discussing the role of business in climate change, providing a profound theoretical background and a skills training to negotiations, as well as the two-day role play itself. This mixed teaching model results in deeper knowledge and understanding of climate related issues but also in getting a more holistic overview of the complexity and interconnectedness of sustainability problems.

Beyond theoretical knowledge, students learn several skills, relating to multilateral negotiations, cooperating in smaller and bigger teams, elaborating common solutions and managing conflict situations. At the end of the course, students have to reflect on the whole experience, focusing on their own contribution, lessons learnt, skills which need further improvement and individual takeaways. This self-reflection is the final, but one of the most important step of creating long-lasting learning outcomes.

3.2 Teaching through consultation projects with the participation of civil sector organisations (NGOs)

In recent years, the practical aspects of higher education have increased in importance and both students and employers demand knowledge, which can be utilised directly and immediately in real life situations. The tackling of sustainability related problems also requires practical solutions rather than the continuous re-iteration of theoretical considerations.

One way of bringing real world problems into the classroom is cooperating with different types of organisations and working with them to solve their problems with the participation of students.

Such an approach has been used in the education of management students at the Corvinus University of Budapest within the framework of the master course titled „Corporate Sustainability and CSR”. The Pro Bono project, integrated into the course, can be best described as a one semester long journey through which participating students carry out a project, together with a consultancy company, targeted at a civil organisation, with the academic support of the instructor of the course. Based on the experiences of running the Pro Bono projects for three years, the innovative approach taken by the course can help students gain a deeper understanding of the meaning of sustainability and the solutions available to society.

The task of the students during the course is twofold. Based on the project scope defined together with the civil organisation, student groups have to deliver solutions to the problems of the organisation using the mentorship of the consultancy business. At the end of the project, students present their results in front of the entire project team.

Meanwhile, students receive useful insights during the classes and elaborate a related assignment, based on predefined criteria of sustainability performance evaluation. The assignment consists of a team presentation and a reflection paper.

Team presentations include the following aspects:

- The analysis, carried out during the project, based on the problem statement and targets set by the student group, the civil organisation and the consultancy company.
- Evaluation of results by providing a SWOT analysis regarding the implementation of the suggested solutions to the problem statement.
- Setting up KPIs for performance evaluation of the activities of the NGO, including KPIs, which are related to responsibility and sustainability.
- Exploring the perception of the society regarding the “business model” and “value creation” of the civil organisation. Suggestions to increase visibility and acceptance.

- Discussing the expected impacts of the successful implementation of the project, from business and social points of view. Considering possible trade-offs between economic and social goals as well as outcomes, related to the project.
- Formulating suggestions for the civil organisation to demolish possible barriers to long-term success and proposing ways of future collaboration between such organisations and the society.

Reflection papers should provide a 5 to 6 page long reflection of the team, on the problem statement, the target setting, the process itself, communication with the civil organisation and the consultancy company, the different roles (with the students' role in focus) and features of the workflow (how the team approached the issue and the whole project). Furthermore, main lessons learnt, identified success factors, suggestions for future Pro Bono Projects, and any other takeaways are formulated.

The expected impact of integrating the Pro Bono project into the CSR course is to ensure long-lasting learning outcomes using a real project as an example and to make students better understand the difficulties and challenges of an intensive collaboration with civil organisations and other types of organisations.

There are some clear lessons learnt from Pro Bono projects. The scope of the project has to be clearly specified. To identify the problem and understand the main scope of the project are often challenging in Pro Bono projects. Project planning and time management are important to achieve results on time and in high quality. Visiting the NGO and getting involved in its everyday operation proved to be very useful, not only for better understanding of the scope of the project and mutual acceptance, but also to become more sensitive to social issues and the main mission of the civil organisation.

During the project, it is necessary to gather first-hand information and start asking for data as early as possible. Pro Bono project teams should be prepared that the NGO does not collect and track all its data in a consistent way, as compared to a company.

To have more contact persons at the NGO side seems necessary, for the sake of facing different opinions and ensuring a higher probability of implementing the resulting ideas of the project. Adaptation of the student team to the contact persons and the organization is crucial. Students often realise the hardship of working with several stakeholders and it is a very important learning outcome how to manage this effectively.

Continuous communication and validation of the ideas and solutions with the NGO is vital. Students have to learn how to ask the right questions to understand the underlying issues as the terminology, the language, the way of thinking and decision making at an NGO may be completely different from what students usually learn about organisations during their studies.

The consultancy company (mentor) is necessary and should be supportive during the whole project in order to facilitate a fruitful and effective cooperation between the student team and the NGO. In a Pro Bono project, students have the chance to learn how to approach a consulting project, narrow it down to a reasonable scope that would be attainable within the given period, and identify solutions for existing problems of an NGO.

Main benefits of embedding Pro Bono projects into a course with strong focus on sustainability and responsibility stem from the synergic effects of acquiring knowledge

about sustainability while, at the same time, making use of the theories in real situations, at real problems, with the aim of providing creative and feasible solutions.

3.3. Social innovation labs

Innovation is at the forefront of the activities of many institutions of higher education. This is especially true in STEM universities, where both students and staff actively participate in technological innovation projects in order to accumulate knowledge as well as to seek funding.

Innovation processes and their results, however, can only be interpreted in their economic, social and natural surroundings.

First, technological innovations should be examined from the various aspects of sustainability. What are the environmental and social implications of a new process innovation? Are new products and services developed less harmful to the eco-systems during their full life-cycles? How do they influence consumer behaviour? How do they effect different social groups?

Second, technological innovations directly aiming at the solution sustainability issues should be developed with the participation of relevant stakeholders. Businesses and the civil sector should collaborate to work out viable solutions to environmental and social problems. Governments should facilitate change and make required resources available.

Third, social innovation should be fostered in order to facilitate change towards a more sustainable society.

Social innovation includes 'new social practices created from collective, intentional, and goal-oriented actions aimed at prompting social change through the reconfiguration of how social goals are accomplished' [20].

Social innovation is an outcome-oriented, collaborative process which is able to deliver effective and relevant solutions by responding to pressing challenges and being a mechanism for achieving systemic change [21].

Murray et al. summarise ways to design, develop and grow social innovation, which is an inspirational open book for initiating social innovation labs, which have sprung up in recent years at many institutions of higher education [22].

Social innovation labs generate solutions to societal challenges including many sustainability issues. These solutions can be new products; new ways of doing things (e.g. processes, regulations, strategies); new structures of resource allocation; and new organizational models [23].

Social innovation labs generate new networks (developing initiatives for long-lasting problem-solving and building high-trust relationships between members of a peer-group for a specific problem); capacity-building (advancing the lab-participant's capacities to enable problem-solving) and knowledge provision (knowledge and perspective exchange between different stakeholders) ([23]).

According to Tiesinga et al., social innovation labs (SI-Labs) have four levels of impact:

- "Impact at the level of the lab itself as a manifestation of a new social practice which changes and enables new ways how problems are solved in contrast to the "state of the art without a lab".

- Existing SI-Labs often inspire the creation of other SI-Labs or are directly involved in the generation of spin-off labs.
- Impact on the level of new social innovation initiatives and the “innovators and change-makers” who have been empowered through the SI-Lab process.
- SI-Labs tell their stories about the ways in which they have solved challenging problems. These emerging narratives help to understand the complexity of societal problems and the work of SI-Labs and, finally, allow to see the necessity of the existence of SI-Labs.” ([24] in: [25] Wascher et al, 2018)

STEM universities, such as the Budapest University of Technology and Economics, are ideal scenes for setting up and operating social innovation labs. The co-existence of different disciplines can give rise to new ideas and can help their implementation to tackle real world problems. Social innovation labs can facilitate collaboration between faculties, between students and professors, as well between academia and other sectors, such as civil society and businesses. As such, social innovation labs can bring together the best of both worlds: facilitate effective learning and foster societal change at a larger scale.

4. FINDINGS AND CONCLUSIONS

The main objective of this paper was to highlight the necessity of shifting the education of Sustainable Development from traditional teaching methods to innovative ones, which are able to provide profound, long-lasting and exceptional learning outcomes for students – for the sake of evoking real change.

The analysis of the literature shows that sustainability issues are typical ‘wicked problems’, which are difficult to solve and need a specific mind-set to manage the complexity, the uncertainty and the strong interconnectedness of those issues. Implications for higher education suggest the requirement of integrating systemic and holistic thinking and radically innovative ways of teaching into study programs and courses. Traditional teaching methods have clear limitations in evoking behavioural change, while an intensive engagement of students is a significant factor in both constructive thinking and behavioural change.

Based on a 25 years of experience in teaching Sustainable Development, the authors described three innovative teaching methods – focusing on their objectives, requirements, learning outcomes and lessons learnt.

Role plays and simulation games prove to be very effective in deepening the knowledge in specific fields, while developing and practicing negotiation skills, multilateral decision making and elaborating consensus solutions to difficult real life problems. To meet the requirements of such role plays is demanding, but the enthusiasm and the reflections of students prove the high impact of this innovative method.

The experience of Pro Bono projects shows how important and mutually beneficial it is when different stakeholders – student teams, a consultancy company and an NGO – are working together in a project, the aim of which is to improve the quality and the operation of NGO-related programs which provide high social value and are crucial for a better and more sustainable society. Successful cooperation with NGOs enhances a better social and economic performance of the related projects, while on parallel, it contributes to the development of important soft skills – like sensibility, ethical considerations and responsibility – as well as hard, analytical skills of the participating

students. The course functions as a facilitative surrounding through transferring well-structured knowledge and approaches, as well as providing continuous academic support during the whole project.

Social innovation labs also facilitate cooperation with stakeholders, but are not limited to NGOs: businesses, policymakers and any other interested parties can participate in lab induced projects. Moreover, in a university setting, social innovation labs can also contribute to the sharing of knowledge between the representatives of different disciplines (i.e. engineering, natural sciences and social sciences) within the institutions.

Based on our positive experiences with innovative teaching methods we believe that they should be used in more institutions of higher education all around the world to address sustainability related problems and to be able to implement viable solutions for a better future.

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